

UEA BIO Pre-arrival survey 2023-24

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This document contains the questions and accompanying text used in our pre-arrival survey in September 2023 which was available to all students enrolled on our 'Preparing for your Biology Studies' virtual summer school. This survey received ethical approval from the SCI-Research Ethics Committee at UEA.

What is the Preparing for your Biology Studies course?

This short course aims to help you prepare for living and studying your course in the School of Biological Sciences at UEA. You will work through subject-specific activities here on Blackboard that aim to help you get to know your peers and help you study more effectively when you arrive at UEA.

Understanding your perspective: SURVEY

Before you begin, please fill in this online survey about your experiences prior to arriving at UEA. This will help us to understand your needs and gauge the success of this University Preparation course.

To be completed by: 18th September 2023

This programme has been developed by staff in the School of Biological Sciences to help students get a flying start to their first term and first year at the UEA. This survey is to help us understand what your hopes and concerns about arriving at UEA are -please be honest and frank to make this programme as useful as possible. This programme has been developed by staff in the school of Biological Sciences to help students get a flying start to their first term and first year at the UEA. If you are a new UEA student, please complete this survey, which is designed to help us understand what your hopes and concerns about arriving at UEA are. Please be honest and frank to make this programme as useful as possible.

These questions will also help us understand what content knowledge and skills you already have from your previous education and life experiences.

The information and data that you provide in this form will also enable us to evaluate this programme and establish how we might improve such programmes in the future.

Any data gathered from this survey will only be used in an anonymised and aggregated form. It will be used to help the School of Biological Sciences to continually evaluate its programme of teaching and learning and assess the effectiveness of outreach and projects. We may also present the results of this research in academic journals and symposia.

Before you begin, we would like to remind you that you are under no obligation to answer any of these questions.

1. What year of study are you beginning in 2023-24?

- Foundation Year
 - Year 1
 - Masters
2. This is a question about your gender. Do you currently identify as:
 - Woman/ girl
 - Man/ boy
 - Transwoman/ transgirl
 - Transman/ transboy
 - Non-binary/ genderqueer/ agender/ gender fluid
 - Don't know
 - Prefer not to say
 - other
 3. Have you or anyone in your close family been to university before?
 - Yes
 - No
 4. What is your ethnic group? Choose one option that best describes your ethnic group or background
 5. Did you receive a contextual admissions offer to join UEA?
 - a. Yes
 - b. No
 - c. Prefer not to say
 - d. don't know
 6. Please confirm the Level 3 qualification you completed prior to entering UEA, e.g. A-Level, BTEC, Access to Higher Education (HE Diploma, T-Level, European Baccalaureate, International Baccalaureate, Scottish Highers. Please enter your subjects and final assigned grade, one subject per line. For example, Maths A* or Biology 7
 7. Do you regularly use a diary, planner or timetable?
 - a. Yes
 - b. no
 8. If you do not use a study planner but would like to explore this a study support system, you might find these UEA study support resources useful (available via the QR code – you'll need to be logged into your UEA account for the site to open)
 9. If you do regularly use a diary planner or timetable, please describe what you use it for. If you do not currently use it to support your studies but would like to explore this, you might find these UEA study support resources useful (available via the QR code – you'll need to be logged into your UEA account for the site to open)
 10. Please select any/ all of the following university information events that you engaged with prior to university
 - UEA Open Day
 - UEA Applicant Day
 - Clearing Open Day
 - Other on-campus activity (e.g. visit to campus with school or college)
 - Off-campus activity (e.g. university staff delivering a session at your school or college)
 - other
 11. The UEA is structured into Faculties and Schools. Do you understand this structure?

- Yes
 - No
12. At UEA, you are based in the School of Biological Sciences, within the Faculty of Science. When thinking about your transition to UEA, would you find it more useful to have information about the School of Biological Sciences, the Faculty of Science, or both?
 - a. The School of Biological Sciences
 - b. The Faculty of Science
 - c. Both
 - d. Don't know
 13. What are you expecting to be the main difference between your most recent study experience and university?
 14. What do you expect to be the biggest challenges to university and how will you try to overcome these challenges?
 15. What three words spring to mind when you think about starting university?
 16. What three words spring to mind to describe your emotions around starting university?
 17. How confident do you feel about starting at UEA?
 - Extremely confident
 - Somewhat confident
 - Neutral
 - Somewhat not confident
 - Extremely not confident
 18. What are you most looking forward to about starting university?
 19. What are you most concerned about for university?
 20. What concerns, if any, do you have relating to your academic performance at UEA?
 21. What factors do you anticipate impacting on your ability to fully engage with your studies?
 22. How many hours a week are you expecting to dedicate to your studies?
 23. How many hours a week do you expect to be on campus in taught sessions?
 24. The expectation is that students typically need to spend in the region of 40 hours per week engaging in their studies. This includes teaching, revision, field courses and independent study. Are you aware of any factors that may impact your ability to commit this time to your studies?
 25. How would you score your mental health and wellbeing?
 - Excellent
 - Good
 - Fair
 - Poor
 26. Do you actively engage in activities to improve your mental health? For example, hobbies, mood tracking, exercise, sleep routine
 - Yes
 - No
 27. What are your three strongest skills? For example, listening, note taking, algebra, writing essays, organisation, empathy
 28. What three skills would you most like to improve in preparation for and/or during your time at university?

29. Do you have a long-term illness or condition that you will be managing alongside your studies (including mental health and specific learning needs)?
- Yes
 - No
 - Prefer not to say
30. If you have a long-term illness, or condition, are UEA's Student Services (disability) team aware of this? Note, there is information regarding help available in the 'Student Support' tab in this preparatory course. You can contact Student Support service via their live chat (scan the QR code)
- Yes
 - No
 - Don't know
31. Will you be managing your studies alongside any caring responsibilities?
- Yes
 - No
 - Prefer not to say
32. Will you be in paid employment during your studies?
- Part-time during term time
 - Full-time during term time
 - Full-time during semester breaks
 - Part-time during semester breaks
 - No
 - Don't know
 - Other
33. Will you have your own laptop or computer for university?
- Yes
 - No
34. This is a question about your IT skills. What can you confidently do on a computer?
Please select all that apply:
- Convert a document to a pdf
 - Create a spreadsheet
 - Write a formula within a spreadsheet to create an average
 - Create a text document (e.g. in Word or Pages) for writing an assignment
 - Draw a graph by hand
 - Draw a graph within Excel or R
 - Attend a Teams meeting
 - Make and edit a video to post online
 - Build a website
 - I am not confident using a computer
35. Do you grant us permission to link your work on this programme to your university progress? If yes, please write your name below (do not write yes). If no, please leave the box blank.